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Title: SOP for GC ISQ 7000 Single Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer - Turning on, calibration, tuning, and shutting down the system

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Summary

This section describes the Turning on, Tuning, Calibration, and Shutting down of GC ISQ 7000.

IMPORTANT

Always make a note about positive/negative calibration and tune the MS to the Logbook on the desktop of the ISQ computer.

Always turn on GC first!

Turning on the GC-ISQ system

1. Turn on the computer and wait for it to be **ON**
2. Check the oil level in the vacuum pump below the table.
3. Open the main valve of the helium bottle to reach the requested pressure of 5 bars (Figure 1)

Figure 1 - Pressure and the filling of the pressure bottle

NOTE: The main valve is open during measurement and standby mode; turn off the main valve only after shutting down GC ISQ 7000. When shutting down ISQ 7000, manipulate only with the main valve; use a small valve for pressure regulation only!

- GC must be ALWAYS turned on **FIRST** → on the right side at the back of GC is the rocker switch. Put it up to the “ON” position
- Wait until the pressure is stable (this will be shown on the display of GC as **Standby**)
- Turn on the TriPlus autosampler by rocker switches on small black boxes between the PC and MS device (order does not matter here; one of them is the TriPlus power supply, and the second is the power supply for the cooling drawer)
- Turn on MS on the right side at the back of MS by putting the toggle switch up in “ON” position (opposite side as on Figure 2, but otherwise identical)

Figure 2 - Location of the rocker power switch on MS

- Wait till the turbomolecular pump **starts buzzing** (no need for the pump to be turned on separately; it will turn on automatically after turning on the MS)

- Open the Chromeleon program and connect the modules to the computer – switching on the shuffle (red to green) in the tabs: Thermo Scientific GCMS Home, Thermo TriPlus RSH, MSDevice (Figure 3)

Figure 3 - Connecting modules to computer

- In Chromeleon Software, in the tab MSDevice or ISQ 7000 Dashboard (Figure 4), observe the percentage of Turbomolecular Pump vacuum and pressure – wait till the % is at least at 50 %; optimal pressure is 53 mTorr
- Above 50 % vacuum, it should be okay by itself, and we can leave the machine to ramp up to 100 % (presence of operator not needed at this time)

Chromeleon Software

ISQ 7000 Dashboard

Figure 4 - Checking of the turbomolecular pump function

- After reaching 100 %, gas flow can be **turned on**, and temperatures for the bakeout can be set (Table 1)

NOTE: Gas flow can be set on the display of GC under Instrument control or in Chromeleon under the tab Front Inlet (or Back Inlet if used). Temperatures can be set for the injector and oven either on the display of GC itself or in Chromeleon under relevant tabs (Front inlet or Oven). Temperatures of the Transfer Line and Ion Source (MS parts in general) can be changed **only** in the Dashboard on the PC in Instrument Control mode.

NOTE: The temperature of the oven needs to be adjusted based on the type of column and its limits.

Instrument module	Temperature (°C)
Injector (PTV or SSL)	200
Oven (depends on column, here WAX)	80
Transfer Line	250
Ion Source	250

Table 1 - Temperatures settings for bakeout

NOTE: bakeout in case of ISQ MS is just leaving the machine to heat up, ideally overnight at higher temperatures; after bakeout, it can take some time for the machine to stabilize – it depends on the length of the shutdown – the longer the shutdown, the longer the bakeout (check it in the Water/Air tune, water should not be too high (Figure 5))

13. After bakeout, check, tune, and calibrate the system (in the next section)

Instrument check before measurement

1. Check the pressure and the filling of the gas bottle
(Figure 1)
2. Check the oil level in the vacuum pump (Edwards below the table)

ISQ 7000 Dashboard system check

1. Open the ISQ 7000 Dashboard → ✓ Status: Idle (Figure 5) → Instrument is in **ON** mode and communicates with the computer

NOTE: For optimum stability, you should start tuning after the lights on the instrument are **green**.

Then, the instrument reached a vacuum and reached the last set temperature. If the instrument has been powered off for a more extended period (cold system), it will take a longer time (up to 4 hours or typically overnight) to reach a stable vacuum and temperature.

Figure 5 – Optimal visual of ISQ 7000 Dashboard

TROUBLESHOOTING: Lights on the instrument are green, but the status is not Idle (✗Communication lost) → communication problem between the ISQ 7000 and PC → Restart the PC → IDLE ✓

- if the system is still not working → turn off the PC → Reset ISQ 7000 → open the front cover of MS by gentle pull and press the button (Figure 6)

NOTE: The reset button (Figure 6) will reset the ISQ 7000 system completely, including the vacuum pump here, wait for the pressure and vacuum to be stable – check on the computer in Chromeleon in tab MSDevice (Figure 4)

Figure 6 - Reset button on the ISQ MS

2. Check the status of the Analyser just above the green
3. “Status: Idle” sign (Temperatures, Repeller, Filament, Lenses, Ion guide, Q1, Dynode/Multiplier Analyzer; Power supply, and Maintenance (Figure 5)

NOTE: Foreline pressure is typically 53 mTorr; Temperatures are adjustable (Table 1).

Calibration and tuning of the system

Checking Air & Water/Tune

Check the air/water spectra of the ISQ 7000 system if the instrument has been powered off/on for a longer period after maintenance – e.g., change of the column or cleaning of the source, or before running additional diagnostics.

1. Press Air & Water / Tune → Spectra → Air → click to “Start scan” (Figure 7)

Figure 7 - ISQ Manual Tune – Air & Water Tune

NOTE: For checking the background of the spectrum, typical ions are present at the following masses:

water = 18

N_2 = 28

O_2 = 32 Present and < abundance than N_2

Typical ions still have the same ratio of N_2/O_2 and N_2/O_2 to water and stable relative abundance.

TROUBLESHOOTING: Leak in a system – see SOP for replacing GC column and GC maintenance.

2. Spectra → Full → Start Scan

NOTE: Check if the full scan spectrum is continuous; relative abundance is typically $5E+04$ (Figure 8)

3. Cal. Gas level → EI

Figure 8 - Full scan tune spectrum

NOTE: After decreasing the noise, check that all the calibration masses are present in spectra m/z : 69 (the highest intensity); 131; 219; 264; 414; 502; 614 (Figure 9)

Figure 9 – Spectrum of calibration gas

NOTE: Relative intensity is typically $1 \cdot 10^7$; $S/N > 1,5$ order (ratio between peak intensities on Figure 9 and Figure 8).

4. Check the resolution of the main peak and its isotope (see Fig 7)
5. Cal. Gas level → Off

6. Stop Scan
7. ISQ 7000 Dashboard → AutoTune → EI Diagnostics
(default) → Start → after “tuning completed
successfully” → OK (Figure 10)

NOTE: Always check the electronics in MS; proceed after the source cleaning or after the shutdown. There is also the possibility to check the repeller voltage in Air & Water Tune – click the bar “Repeller” and try different voltages (e.g., 3 eV – 10 eV); if the intensities and ratio of calibration masses (Figure 9) are changing.

Figure 10 - AutoTune - EI Diagnostics

8. ISQ 7000 Dashboard → View Tune Report → Save Report to PDF → TUNE → ISQ Tune Diagnostic EI → year (e.g. 2022) → format YYMMDD

ISQ Tune Results

Lab: Recetox
 Tune Completed - Mon Nov 7 11:00:53 2022
 Tune File: Diagnostics_EI_2022-11-07-11-00-53.isqtune
 Tune Type: EI Diagnostics (default)
 Starting Tune File: (Last Saved Tune)

Instrument Name: ISQ
 Instrument ID: 2104078
 User: ISQ7000

1 – shape and resolution of isotopes

Ion Source Type	EI
Polarity	Positive
Electron Lens Voltage	5 V
Electron Energy	70 eV
Emission Current	50 µA
Ion Guide Frequency	1683.5
Q1 Frequency	1086.4
Multiplier Voltage	1175.5 V
Detector Gain	2.2 x 10 ⁻⁵
MS Transfer Line	200.0 °C
Filament Selection	1
Ion Source Temperature	200.0 °C
Foreline Pressure	52 mTorr

2 – multiplier voltage

Full Scan Spectrum Not Acquired

Mass	Theory	Abundance	Relative Abundance	Isotope Mass	Theoretical Isotope Mass	Isotope Abundance	Isotope Ratio
69.03	69.00	9,093,083	100.00	70.05	70.00	101,694	1.12
219.01	218.99	3,490,184	38.38	220.03	219.99	144,995	4.15
501.98	501.97	214,827	2.36	503.02	502.97	19,353	9.01

Air/ Water Check:

H2O (%18/99)	16.78
N2 (%28/99)	34.36
O2 (%32/99)	22.55
CO2 (%44/99)	1.57
N2 / H2O (%28/18)	2.05

Leak Check: 7.13% of reference

3 – leak check

Figure 11 - ISQ Tune Result - page 1

NOTE: After tuning the instrument, check the ISQ Tune Results pages 1 (Figure 11) and 2 (Error! Reference source not found.).

Multiplier Voltage: maximum 2000 V

Detectors gain typically 2.10⁵ (adjustable value)

Leak check max 10 % (ideal 2-3 %) – but can differ with more sensitive columns, e.g., PEG columns (WAX, Nukol, ...) will have leak oscillating around 10 % at the least, usual Sil columns should be around 2-3 %

ISQ Tune Results

Lab: Recetox
 Tune Completed - Mon Nov 7 11:00:53 2022
 Tune File: Diagnostics_EI_2022-11-07-11-00-53.isqtune
 Tune Type: EI Diagnostics (default)
 Starting Tune File: (Last Saved Tune)

Instrument Name: ISQ
 Instrument ID: 2104078
 User: ISQ7000

Diagnostics

Filament Check	Pass
Lens Check	Pass
Leak Check	Pass
Power Supply Check	Pass
RFDC Check	Pass
Temperature Check	Pass
Detector Check	Pass
Vacuum Check	Pass
Communication Check	Pass
Ion Guide Frequency Check	Pass
Q1 Frequency Check	Pass

Figure 12 - ISQ Tune Results, page 2

EI Tune (default)

After cleaning the EI source or maintenance/before the big sample set, a shortened version of the EI Full Tune is recommended. It is also suitable for daily tuning. The EI Check is more than enough to check the leak only.

This tunes resolution, mass, and lenses and adjusts detector sensitivity but does not tune detector gain.

Figure 13 - ISQ EI Tunes - types and their usage

1. ISQ 7000 Dashboard → AutoTune → EI Tune (default)
→ Start (Figure 13)
2. ISQ 7000 Dashboard → View Tune Report → Save
Report to PDF → TUNE → ISQ Tune Diagnostic EI →
year (e.g.2022) → format YYMMDD

Repeller voltage (ideal value = 3 – 8, higher value means dirty source → check after every measuring;
> 8 → clean the source)

NOTE: There is also the possibility of creating your tune program with personalized parameters for the method. Click on the “Tune Types” tab and select some Tuning file – e.g., EI Tune. Then click Edit and start editing the parameters, e.g., lowering the m/z range measured or just choosing the check of the leak, changing the SIM ions considering the fact around which mass we are planning to measure – around the highest mass it will be the most sensitive so in case of measuring lower Mw molecules, get rid of those higher masses like 502 – in this case 264 should be completely fine. NEVER change the quadrupole voltage.

Shutting down of the GC-MS system

1. Cool down the GC oven and injector via Chromeleon Software or directly on the screen of the GC. Let the gas still flow so the destruction of the column caused by its absence does not occur. See the GC documentation for information.
2. Open the ISQ 7000 Dashboard and click Shut Down (Figure 14). The confirmation box appears; click the “Yes” button.

Figure 14 - Shut down of MS

During the shutdown procedure, the vacuum and heater lights will remain off. Once the procedure is complete and the instrument is ready to be powered off, the power light will turn amber and start blinking rapidly. At this point, it is safe to power off the ISQ 7000 system.

3. On the right-hand upper corner of the back of the instrument (Figure 2), push down the rocker switch to power off the ISQ 7000 system.
4. Open the GC oven door slightly to help the instrument to cool down completely.
5. Use a rocker switch to also turn off other connected components – GC and autosampler, if used. Make sure everything is in the “Off” position.
6. Close the main valve of the gas cylinder (Figure 1).